

Industrial processing of rice husk for environment, energy and economy

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Abstract : An approach for comprehensive and efficient utilization of Rice Husk (RH) integrating the three E's – Environment, Energy and Economy has been outlined based on experimental information. RH can be thermally processed for co-production of *metal-impregnated or chemically modified active solid silica-carbon composites* with simultaneous recovery of liquid and gaseous by-products accounting for about 80–90% of the biomass with minimum addition to environmental pollution.

The active and amorphous silica-carbon composite solid can be used in systems for removing waterborne and airborne toxic substances like phenol, hexavalent chromium, fluoride and arsenic in water and vapours of acetone, chloroform, benzene and pyridine. Liquid condensate collected during processing is a rich source of various useful organic chemicals. The third bulk co-product, a combustible gas of low calorific value, can supplement the energy requirements of the process.

The spent *silicarbons*, after use in pollution abatement systems may be suitably formulated and melted into stable glass thus solving one of the major problems of ultimate disposal of toxic-loaded solid wastes generated.

Small industries handling ~60 MT RH annually appear to be just viable. As ancillaries to rice mills they are likely to prove handsomely rewarding. Projected estimates further indicate that industrial processing in the suggested mode, of only 10% of India's annual RH biomass (~4 Million Metric Tons), has the potential of generating ~200000 employments in ~66000 small decentralised units. The estimated capital investment is in the order of Rs. 6600 crores.

Keywords : Rice Husk, industrial processing, carbon credit.

The present level of annual paddy production in the world is about 600 million metric tons. India's share in the annual production rate is about 120 million tons. Rice Husk (RH), accounts for about one third of total mass of paddy and is a by-product of paddy processing operations. It contains, like other plant biomasses, cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin but it also contains, unlike most other plant biomasses, about 15–20% silica and so it may be considered a special biomass. The bulk of Indian RH is used as fuel supplement in households and in small rice-mills. The resulting pollution from the non-point sources has been a matter of serious concern.

A wealth of information and knowledge has been accumulated on the utilization of RH. Govindarao¹ reviewed comprehensively the earlier phases of work. Researchers are still taking tremendous interest in exploring newer, better and more efficient modes of utilization of this agricultural waste. The major application-areas involve thermal processing of RH to derive active carbonaceous materials^{2–6}, silica and ceramics^{6–15} and harnessing energy by combustion and gasification^{14,16–20}.

Vigorous R&D efforts notwithstanding, RH continues to be a matter of concern for polluting the environment.

When, for example, silica-free carbon or carbon free silica/ash is the target material, only about 15–20% of dry husk is recovered. Recovery may go up to 30–40% when silica and carbon are combined in the form of a composite solid product. During thermal processing aimed at production of these solid products liquid and gaseous fractions of varying amounts and compositions escape in the environment. During combustion or gasification huge quantities of *ash*, often mixed with unburnt or partly burnt residues, get accumulated posing great disposal problems, if not planned specially to be used^{11,21–23}.

Attempts at better and fuller utilization of RH biomass exploiting the accumulated R&D findings have not met with much success.

This work outlines an approach for comprehensive and efficient utilization of RH integrating the three E's – Environment, Energy and Economy emphasizing on co-production of *metal-impregnated or chemically modified active solid silica-carbon composites* with simultaneous recovery of liquid and gaseous by-products accounting for about 80–90% of the biomass with minimum addition to the burden of environmental pollution during processing.

Fig. 1. Scheme of utilization of Rice Husk for Environment, Energy and Economy.

Table 1. Product-yields of thermal processing of Rice Husk

Pre-treatment	Silica-carbon char, yield (% of dry RH)	Liquid condensate, yield (% of dry RH)	Gas yield Litre/100 g dry RH at NTP	Remarks
Untreated	35–44	32–36	6.0–6.5	Emissions at 300–600 °C
Metal-impregnated	37–45	26–34	5.4–6.0	Emissions tend to stop at ~550 °C
Sulphuric acid	43–46	23–26	–	Pre-treated RH blackens
Sodium carbonate	40–45	26–29	6.4–6.8	Emissions in two stages

The active silica-carbon solid can be used in systems for combating aqueous and gaseous pollution in general and for removing waterborne and airborne toxic substances (both organic and inorganic) in particular. Various useful organic chemicals and a tarry residue can be isolated from the liquid condensate collected during thermal processing of untreated/chemically pre-treated RH. A combustible gas of low calorific value with ample scope for betterment constitutes the third major product.

Results and discussion

The relative yields (ranges for three experiments) of the three primary products are summarised in Table 1. Some properties (mean/range of at least three

Table 2. Some properties of the solid carbonaceous products

Sample (carbonaceous solid)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Moisture content (%)	pH of 1% suspension	Iodine No.	Surface area (BET), m ² /g	Ash (% of dry carbonaceous solid)	Notes
Untreated	0.113	3.5	8.5	75	95	51.2	–
Metal impregnated	0.110–0.115	3.4–4.6	8.2–8.9	70–140	100–170	48–51	–
Sulphuric acid	0.111	3.7	8.3	69	65	–	–
Sodium carbonate	–	–	–	–	–	62.5 ¹	¹ Greenish glass
RH Carbon (silica leached)	0.110	3.9	8.8	80	97	4.9 ²	² Non-silica components
RH	0.152	7.8	7.8	–	–	19.6	–

measurements) of the RH-derived active silica-carbon (RHSC) solid products are shown in Table 2. Table 3 shows the proportions of the three physical fractions that were obtained from 70 g of cold-trapped condensates collected during thermal processing of iron impregnated RH. It also shows the proportion of organic liquid mix that could be distilled out of the light coloured aqueous fraction. It is well documented that various organic chemicals (acetic acid, furfural etc.) can be derived from RH^{24,25}. The data in Table 1 and Table 3 indicate that ~10% of RH (dry mass) is recoverable as organic liquids. The relative proportions of the three fractions of the cold-trapped condensates (Table 3) are expected to vary from batch to batch and they are also amenable to control to a certain extent²⁶.

Table 3. Characteristics of fractions of condensate (iron impregnated RH)

% Condensate,	Aqueous part	Oily-tarry part, % condensate	Residue % condensate
	Distilled fraction (128–140 °C)		
pH		19.40	2.24
	% aqueous part, pH		
78.36	65		
4.6–5.0	5.5–6.5		

The oily-tarry part of the condensate was found to be insoluble in benzene, toluene and kerosene. It was ~20% soluble in rectified spirit and ~80% soluble in acetone. The acetone extract, after ignition at 550 °C, left 5.5% carbonaceous residue.

Table 4. Rice Husk Gas : Dependence of combustible components on pre-treatment

Gas from batch	Combustibility	Methane content (vol %)	Carbon monoxide (vol %)
Untreated RH	Blue flame	0.31	4.4
Iron-manganese treated	Blue flame	2.83	2.0
Sod carbonate treated	Reddish-blue flame	0.45	2.3

The silica present in RH is retained integrated in the carbonaceous solids that maintain the original husk-shape and may be treated as granular but are of low strength. Carbon and silica (plus minor inorganic constituents) in the solids are approximately in the ratio 1 : 1 by wt. (Table 2) and are primarily non-crystalline, as revealed by XRD of the solid.

The composition of the gases, especially the fuel components like CH₄ and CO are amenable to changes (Table 4 showing the mean of three gas samples of each type) that may be favourably controlled^{18,27} to render the

gas into a significant supplementary fuel. The gas may also be enriched externally in fuel constituents.

Table 5. Sorption from aqueous solution

Sorbent	Time (min) for max effect	Contaminant	Initial concn. (ppm)	Final concn.	% Pick up
RHSC-Zn	15	Phenol	8.0	0.60	92.8
Comm coco C	15	Phenol	10	1.89	82.1
RHSC-Fe	10	Cr ⁶⁺	10	1.41	85.9
Comm coco C	10	Cr ⁶⁺	10	2.43	75.7
RHSC-SA	10	F ⁻	5	2.1	58.0
RHC	10	F ⁻	5	2.8	45.0
Comm coco C	10	F ⁻	5	2.35	33.0
RHSC-Ag	10	As	0.5	0.15	70.0
Comm coco C	10	As	0.5	0.24	52.0
RHC	10	As	0.5	0.20	60.0
RH-silica	10	As	0.5	0.06	88.0
Act alumina	10	As	0.5	0.09	82.0
RH	10	As	0.5	0.23	54.0
RHSC-Fe	15	As (AsO ₄) ³⁻	1.2	0.9	26.2
RHSC-Fe	15	As (AsO ₃) ³⁻	1.0	0.31	69.0

Activated solid materials (carbon with or without silica, ash, carbon-free silica) have been shown^{28–34} to act as effective sorbents for toxic and hazardous substances in water and air/flue gases.

Table 6. Sorption of organic vapors

Sorbent	Organic vapor	Flow rate of vapor (g/min)	Saturn time, min	Pick up (mg/g sorbent)
RHSC-Fe	Acetone	0.71	20	73
	Chloroform	0.40	20	125
	Benzene	0.18	15	75
RHSC-U	Pyridine	0.06	20	70
	Benzene	0.17	40	39
Com active carbon (coconut shell)	Pyridine	0.05	30	20
	Acetone	0.47	30	70
	Chloroform	0.95	30	34

The amorphous silica leached out from RHSC's are found to be active in sorbing certain substances from aqueous and gaseous streams. Silica present in RHSC's probably plays a very important role in the *activity* of these products. It may be noted (Table 2) that RH carbon free from silica, RHC, shows iodine number and BET-surface area that are no better than most of the other solids

containing silica. Based on these considerations it is preferable to distinguish the silica containing carbonaceous solids derived from RH as **active silicarbon** and not as simple *active carbons* or carbon-silica *composite*.

Results of tests (mean of 3–5 tests for each) demonstrate activity and effectiveness of RHSC's in sorbing out toxic organic and inorganic substances from aqueous solutions and volatile organic compounds (VOCs)/gases from air and are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 7. Glass formation with different carbonaceous solids

Batch mix	Max. temp. (°C)	Wt. of glass (g)	Approx composition of glass (calculated) (wt %)	Appearance of glass
RHSC-U : 2.24 g	950	1.91	SiO ₂ : 44.8 Na ₂ O : 50.2	Pale violet, hygroscopic,
Na ₂ CO ₃ : 1.984 g			Others : 4.9	soluble in water
RHSC-U : 1.417 g	1100	0.78	SiO ₂ : 70.6 Na ₂ O : 21.7	Greenish, transparent,
Na ₂ CO ₃ : 0.337 g			Others : 7.7	insoluble in water, stable
RHSC-Mn : 0.99 g	1200	0.53	SiO ₂ : 74.9 Na ₂ O : 16.7	Almost colorless, transparent,
Na ₂ CO ₃ : 0.17 g			Others : 8.3	insoluble in water, stable

It was suggested that *siliceous ash* from RH might be used by glass industries²¹. Although processes for preparing sodium silicate (water glass) and potassium silicate have been reported^{22,23} they have not been used industrially.

Experiments in our laboratory clearly demonstrate that silica in the solid SiO₂-C composites when exhausted by picking up toxic organic and/or inorganic substances may be converted into water-soluble alkali silicate glasses or into stable and durable glass by adjustment of the compositions (vide Table 7) before being melted. The minor inorganic constituents of RH and the impregnated metals both contribute to the durability of the glass. Glass formation is energy-saving as it takes place at lower temperatures compared to those required for ordinary glass-making. As the carbon in the solid burns releasing energy and gases *in situ* refining and homogenisation of the glass also take place. In the process the sorbed organics

may get incinerated and toxic inorganics may be largely retained in the glass – certainly a desirable option for disposal of the spent solid silicarbon wastes loaded with toxic/hazardous substances.

Table 8. Costs involved in the suggested mode of RH processing

Cost head	Amount Rs./MT	Justifications
RH Procurement	600/-	Nominally priced (~Rs. 0.50/kg), transportation of bulk RH
Processing [fuel (LPG), salaries and wages for 3 heads, overhead, maintenance etc.]	6000/-	Based on personal information collected from industries using RH as major boiler fuel and on estimated fuel (commercial LPG) cost (Rs. 50/- per kg, C.V. 11000 kcal/M ³); sp. heat of RH : 0.4 cal/g/°C
Depreciation on plant	2000/-	An estimated cost of plant : Rs.12 lacs; Depreciation @ 10% per yr.

Total cost : Rs. 8600/- per MT RH processed.

The present work, therefore, outlines a single-step dynamic and relatively quick method of thermal treatment of RH chemically pre-treated or pre-impregnated with metal salts that gives three primary bulk products simultaneously. It also demonstrates that stable and durable glass can be obtained from the spent RH-*silicarbons*. All these may be translated into practice in an integrated plant (schematically shown in Fig. 1) to improve upon the economy of RH utilization.

Economic considerations :

Based on the results of our studies and those of other workers, we are inclined to propose setting up of RH processing plants near, or still better, with Rice Mills. The two bulk-products – metal-impregnated or chemically modified active silica-carbon soft granular composite solid, the *silicarbon* and the liquid condensate – can be sold out. The third product – a combustible gas of low calorific value – may be used as a supplementary energy source in the site itself. However, it can also be improved and/or enriched.

On the basis of 1 metric ton of RH processed a preliminary estimate of the costs involved in a plant processing 200 kg RH per day (5 MT RH per month or 60 MT RH/yr, 300 work-days/yr) is presented in Table 8.

The overhead costs may be significantly reduced if the industry runs as an ancillary to a rice mill.

Table 9. Estimated financial returns (per MT RH processed)

Product/Item	Quantity	Returns (Rs.)	Justifications/Basis
Solid RHSC	300 kg	9000	Rs. 30/- per kg is a reasonable selling price (Activated carbons sale at ~Rs. 40-90/- per kg, wood charcoal sales at ~Rs. 20/kg)
Org liq mix	100 kg	1000	A nominal selling price @ Rs.10/- per kg presumed; likely to increase
Tar	50 kg	500	@ Rs. 10/- per kg; may be used as a protective paint or as fuel supplement
Gas	6 M ³	10	C.V. of the gas is too low (300-400 kcal/M ³) to sell; may supplement fuel consumption. C.V. may be improved
Carbon Credit	0.55 Unit	400	Euro 14-15 per C-Credit (reduction of 1 MT of CO ₂ emission)

Total returns : Rs. 10910/- per MT RH processed.

Financial returns derivable are projected in a tabular form (Table 9).

It is, therefore, likely to prove a profitable industry. The above estimates do not take into account the other benefits, viz.

- At least 3 jobs created per plant (processing ~60 MT RH annually)
- At least 215 kg (per MT RH) useful glass immobilizing toxic substances
- Toxic and/or hazardous pollution abated
- Decentralised and rural industrial development

The visions may be extended a little further : if only 10% of the RH generated annually in India can be processed in the mode outlined here, it is easily worked out that

- 4 Million Metric Tons (MMT) RH may be used in an industrial mode in ~66000 small units distributed all over the country
- ~200000 jobs will be created
- ~Rs.1.7 billions (170 crores) can be earned annually on Carbon Credits
- Annually ~1.2 MMT of *active silicarbon* will be made available locally to combat pollution and to treat drinking water contributing to improved public health.

Small-scale biomass gasifiers for developing countries have received attention from UNDP/WB³⁵. The problems are also recognized. The proposed mode of RH utilization is expected to prove an equally good, if not better, option.

Of late (2006), India's continued interest is reflected in the constitution of a **National Mission on Decentralized Biomass Energy for villages and industries** in which RH features prominently. In fact, alongside widespread open burning in households and small enterprises (especially Rice Mills), industrial exploitation has also started. Some medium industries (such as vegetable oil processing) have adopted RH as a major fuel for their boiler operations at lower costs. About 50 companies including some rice mills have installed captive generators based on RH gas generated *in situ* in gasifiers.

If the envisaged mode of utilization of RH is dedicatedly pursued and the objectives are realised it is likely to contribute towards sustainable development. The visions of our **National Mission on Decentralized Biomass Energy for villages and industries** will be fulfilled ensuring

- Transformation of waste to wealth
- Minimization of environmental degradation through widespread burning of RH
- Decentralization of rural and industrial energy supplement
- Supply of an enormous source of a *sorbent* capable of removing toxic/hazardous substances from water and air
- Decontamination of drinking water to help improve public health
- Enhance national energy security
- Employment generation, particularly in rural areas

Materials and methods :

Experiments have been carried out on thermal processing of chemically pre-treated RH to derive an active silica-carbon char residue, a liquid condensate from the volatiles and a combustible gas through a single step processing in a small laboratory set-up. Chemical pre-treatment included single metal impregnation (1 wt% of elemental metal, dry RH basis), mixed metal impregnation (1% of each metal), sulphuric acid treatment (dry husk soaked in 5% sulphuric acid for 4 h) and sodium carbonate

treatment (anhydrous sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) up to ~35% of dry weight of RH).

Thermal treatment was carried out in a cylindrical mild steel reactor heated at controlled rates up to the desired temperatures (700–900 °C) in an electric muffle furnace. A weighed amount (35–45 g/batch) of dry RH (with or without chemical pre-treatment) was loosely packed in the ms reactor. The outlet tube was connected through an ice-cold trap to a glass jar for collection of gases by displacement of water.

The carbonaceous solids (RHSC) derived by thermal processing of treated and untreated RH were characterized by determining their bulk density, pH of 1% of suspension, iodine number (mg of iodine decolourised by one g of dry carbonaceous solid), surface area (N₂-adsorption (BET) method – Carls-Erba (Italy) 1750 Sorpty), and ash content.

The condensate collected in the ice-cold trap was separated into light coloured aqueous and dark coloured oily-tarry parts and a heavier tar-solid (black) residue; their relative proportions were estimated and were tested for some of their primary characteristics.

The collected gases were tested for combustibility and their methane and carbon monoxide contents were analyzed by gas chromatography.

Aqueous solutions of known concentrations of phenol, hexavalent chromium, fluoride and arsenic were treated with RHSC (0.5–1.0 g), shaken for different durations of time and their concentrations in the filtrate were determined spectrophotometrically following standard procedures³⁶.

Vapours of acetone, chloroform, benzene and pyridine were aspirated through RHSC (1.0–3.0 g) packed glass tubes and the weight-gain of the tubes provided the amount of vapour sorbed.

Conclusion :

The present modes of utilization of rice husk are polluting and wasteful in varying degrees. A more efficient, less polluting and sustainable mode of utilization is required and that is feasible.

References

1. V. M. H. Govindarao, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1980, **39**, 495.
2. Yupeng Guo, Kaifeng Yu, Zichen Wang and Hongding Xu, *Carbon*, 2003, **41**, 1645.
3. L. J. Kennedy, J. J. Vijaya and G. Sekaran, *Ind. Engg. Chem. Res.*, 2004, **43**, 1832.
4. S. Ali, F. A. Chughtai, N. Irum and K. Aftab, *Int. J. Agric. Biol.*, 2002, **4**, 23.
5. D. W. Armstrong, V. J. Flanigan, J. J. William, Jui-Lung Li and K. L. Rundlett, US Pat US 5883040 A 19990316 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1999, **130**, 198461).
6. L. A. Zemnukhova, V. V. Vinogradov, A. A. Bylkov and D. V. Vinogradov, Russ Pat RU 2144498 CI 20000120 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **135**, 34951).
7. S. Chandrasekhar, K. G. Satyanarayana, P. N. Pramada, P. Raghavan and T. N. Gupta, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2003, **38**, 3159.
8. K. Sujirote and P. N. Leangsuwan, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2003, **38**, 4739.
9. J. S. Romano, F. A. Rodrigues, L. T. Bernardi, J. A. Rodrigues and N. Segre, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 2006, **41**, 1775.
10. T. Torikai, T. Ishibashi, K. Egoshi, M. Yada and T. Watari, *Key Engg. Mats.*, 2003, **247** (*Adv. Cream and Composites*), 433.
11. M. K. Naskar and M. Chatterjee, *J. Euro. Cream. Soc.*, 2004, **24**, 3499.
12. C. Real, M. D. Alcalá and J. M. Criado, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2004, **87**, 75.
13. T. Kamio, K. Kawamura, E. Koyama and Y. Nishino, Jap Pat JP 165783 A2 20030610 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2003, **139**, 10859).
14. M. T. McQueen, 'Proc. 17th Int. Conf. Fluidized Bed Comb', 2003, pp. 721-727.
15. Norman D. Hinman and E. Charles Wyman, US Pat Appl. Publ. US 2006089258 A1 20060427 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2006, **144**, 393894).
16. E. Natarajan, A. Nordin and A. N. Rao, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 1998, **14**, 533.
17. M. Fang, L. Yang, G. Chen, Z. Shi, Z. Luo and K. Cen, *Fuel Procg. Technol.*, 2004, **85**, 1273.
18. A. K. Jain, S. K. Sharma and D. Singh, *Ind. Chem. Engineer*, 2002, **44**, 235.
19. M. H. Rei, F. S. Lin and T. B. Su, *Appl. Catal.*, 1986, **26**, 27.
20. L. Armesto, A. Bahillo, K. Veijonen, J. Otero and A. Cabanillas, *Recent Progres en Genie des Procedes* 2000, **14**, 313 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 135:376081).
21. L. B. do Mongest, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1930, **24**, 46954.
22. Xinghan Xu, Ch. Pat CN 1039000 A 19900124 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **113**, 155338).
23. Zhongda Yang, Ch Pat CN 1062513 A 19920708 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **118**, 62614).
24. A. Jain, R. T. Rao, S. S. Sambhi and P. D. Grover, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 1994, **7**, 285.
25. Yung-Shan Guo, Taiwan Pat TW 499406 B 20020821 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2002, **139**, 382964).
26. Tzong-Hong Liou, *Carbon*, 2004, **42**, 785.
27. A. Chakraverty and S. Kaleemullah, *Energy Conversion and Mangmt*, 1991, **32**, 565.
28. Jurui Qi, Zhi Li, Yupeng Guo and Hongding Xu, *Mats. Chem. and Phys.*, 2004, **87**, 96.
29. S. Oyama, H. Aburano, T. Matsumoto, H. Ishizawa, M. Oiwa, E. Ogura *et al.*, Jap Pat JP 2003266064 A2 20030924 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2003, **139**, 265097).
30. K. Srinivasan and N. Balasubramanian, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2003,

- 19, 287.
31. S. Maiti, S. Dey, S. Purakayastha and B. Ghosh, *J. Residuals Science & Technology*, 2005, **2**, 143.
32. K. Kataoka, Jap Pat JP 2003181283 A2 20030702 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2003, **139**, 40974).
33. N. R. Bishnoi, M. Bajaj and N. Sharma, *Environmental Technology*, 2004, **25**, 899.
34. I. G. Gafarov, A. I. Kuznetsov, Yu. I. Rastorguev, V. S. Timofeev, O. N. Hoang Temkin and Bong Kim, Russ Pat RU 2003-127908 20030918 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2005, **143**, 269006).
35. H. A. M. Knoef, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 1999, **18**, 39.
36. L. S. Clesseri, A. E. Greenberg and A. E. Eaton (eds.), "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater", 20th ed., APHA, AWWA and WEF, 1998.